

Community Mapping and Participation Processes in Aotearoa New Zealand

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Community Mapping and Participation Processes in Aotearoa New Zealand

• *TYPE:*
Research

• *LOCALISATION:*
Wellington, New Zealand

• *POPULATION:*
419,000

• *CITY SIZE:*
289.91 Km²

• *COMMUNITY:*
**Newtown, Wellington
Porirua, Wellington**

• *KEY ISSUES:*

- Data from the 1st phase of Online survey.
- Data from the 2nd phase of Focus Groups.
- NZ European, Māori, Chinese and Pasifika.
- Community Participation
- Public Open Space
- Sense of community
- Health and Well-being

Introduction

Waves of Migration

1000 years ago

In 19th century

In 20th century

Colonization and International Migration

■ European ■ Maori ■ Pasifika ■ Chinese ■ Others

European (70.2%)

Māori (16.5%)

Chinese (35.2% of Asian)

Pasifika (8.1%)

Introduction

Community Culturally Diverse

Focus on Public Space

New Threats to Public Open Space

Chinatown

Chinese New Year Celebration

Public Space - Residential

Public Space - Landscape

Public Space - Commercial

Public Space - Fenced

Public Space - Commercialized

Public Space - not for all

Gap and Opportunity

Research Questions

- General Research Question:

Which public open space participatory planning processes can most effectively encourage sense of community for different ethnic groups in New Zealand?

- Specific Research Question 1:

Do community members who take part in the participatory planning process of community parks show higher sense of community than the community members who do not?

- Specific Research Question 2:

What differences are there for European, Māori, Chinese and Pasifika community members in the process of participatory planning for community parks?

The 1st Specific Research Question proposed above is further translated to one detailed hypotheses:

- *Hypotheses:*

People's sense of community will increase most significantly for those, who took part in the participatory process of planning their own community parks, rather than people who did not take part in.

Research Methodology

- The research will be conducted in two principal phases, using a combination of **quantitative** and qualitative research methods.
- Firstly, we examined whether participation processes in the design of public open spaces encourage a sense of community amongst residents, using the long-established **Sense of Community Index**. This phase of the research helps answer the 1st research question.
- During the 2nd phase of the focus groups, we examined people's experiences of participatory planning processes and their outcomes through a sequence of focus groups.

Sense of Community Index

This Sense of Community Index is based on the theory of sense of community presented by McMillan and Chavis that a sense of community was a perception with four elements:

Fulfillment of Needs

Sense of Membership

Influence

Emotional Connection

The 24-question comprised of four dimensions, with 6 questions in each dimension.

Participants rated on a 4-point Likert scale, from 0 - strongly disagree to 3 - strongly agree.

Measurements and Analysis Methods

Measurements		Data Analysis Methods
<i>Sense of Community Index</i>	<i>Reliability Analysis</i>	Cronbach's Alpha
<i>Sample Description (Age, Gender, Educational Background, Ethnicity)</i>		Descriptive Analysis
<i>Sense of Community Index</i>	1) <i>Comparison of Means</i>	Multifactor ANOVA
	2) <i>Comparison of Means</i>	Descriptive Analysis
	3) <i>Comparison of Means</i>	Independent Sample T Test

Data Analysis _ Descriptive Analysis _ Demographic

Demographics		N=145	
		Whether or not	Frequency (N)
Ethnicity			
<i>NZ European</i>	<i>Took part in</i>	41	58.6%
	<i>Not took part in</i>	44	
<i>Māori</i>	<i>Took part in</i>	4	11.7%
	<i>Not took part in</i>	13	
<i>Chinese</i>	<i>Took part in</i>	9	14.5%
	<i>Not took part in</i>	12	
<i>Pasifika</i>	<i>Took part in</i>	4	6.2%
	<i>Not took part in</i>	5	
<i>Others</i>	<i>Took part in</i>	3	9.0%
	<i>Not took part in</i>	10	
Gender			
<i>Male</i>		69	47.6%
<i>Female</i>		73	50.3%
<i>Others</i>		3	2.1%

Demographics		N=145	
		Whether or not	Frequency (N)
Age			
<i>18-25</i>		16	11%
<i>26-35</i>		20	13.8%
<i>36-45</i>		28	19.3%
<i>46-55</i>		25	17.2%
<i>56-65</i>		34	23.4%
<i>Over 65</i>		22	15.2%
Education			
<i>Primary</i>		2	1.4%
<i>Secondary</i>		17	11.7%
<i>Professional</i>		77	53.1%
<i>Masters or Higher</i>		49	33.8%
Whether or not			
<i>Took part in</i>		61	42.1%
<i>Not took part in</i>		84	57.9%

1st Phase Conclusion

2nd Stage of Research

Focus Group Description

Community	Ethnic Group	Location	Number	Duration
<i>Newtown</i>	New Zealand European	Newtown Community Hall	3	01:15:00
		Newtown Community Centre	2	00:36:00
	Chinese	Online through Zoom	5	00:45:00
	New Zealand European	Online through Zoom	4	00:36:00
	Māori	Online through Zoom	3	01:30:00
<i>Porirua</i>	Chinese	Online through Zoom	3	00:45:00
		Online through Zoom	2	00:22:00
	Pasifika	City Hub, Porirua	2	00:45:00
		Online through Zoom	7	01:09:00

Newtown Community & Cultural Centre

City Hub, Porirua

Online through Zoom

Participation Methods Coding

Participation Methods Number

Coding	Participation Methods
<i>No.1</i>	Participatory Mapping
<i>No.2</i>	Guided Tour
<i>No.3</i>	Focus Group
<i>No.4</i>	3D Visualization
<i>No.5</i>	Interactive Planning
<i>No.6</i>	Visual Preference Survey
<i>For Māori</i>	<i>hui</i>
<i>For Pasifika</i>	<i>talanoa</i>

Scale of Effectiveness

Coding	Scale
	① Extremely Effective
✓	② Moderately Effective
	③ Slightly Effective
✗	Least Effective

2nd Phase Conclusion

Scale of Effectiveness

Coding		Scale
	①	Extremely Effective
✓	②	Moderately Effective
	③	Slightly Effective
✗		Least Effective

Ethnic Group	No. 1	No. 2	No. 3	No. 4	No. 5	No. 6	<i>hui</i>	<i>talanoa</i>
<i>New Zealand European</i>	✗	✓		①		✓		
<i>Māori</i>	✗	①	✓			✓	★	
<i>Chinese</i>	✗	✓		✓		①		
<i>Pasifika</i>	✗	①		✓	✓			★

Coding	Participation Methods	Coding	Participation Methods
<i>No.1</i>	Participatory Mapping	<i>No.5</i>	Interactive Planning
<i>No.2</i>	Guided Tour	<i>No.6</i>	Visual Preference Survey
<i>No.3</i>	Focus Group	<i>For Māori</i>	<i>hui</i>
<i>No.4</i>	3D Visualization	<i>For Pasifika</i>	<i>talanoa</i>

Thank you.